

GENOMED4ALL USE CASE META DATA AVAILABLE FOR OPEN SCIENCE

The GenoMed4ALL project

Accumulating evidence points towards personalised medicine to treat and manage common, rare and ultra-rare haematological diseases. Advanced statistics and machine learning approaches may contribute to the exploitation of omics and clinical data in patient-oriented research and decision-making. [GenoMed4ALL is an European project](#), funded under the call “Societal Challenges - Health, demographic change and well-being” with grant agreement ID: 101017549, with start date 1 January 2021 and end date 30 June 2025.

GenoMed4ALL aims to demonstrate the potential and benefits of trustable and explainable AI technologies to exploit the powerful set of “omics” data for advancing research and personalized medicine. The use cases are three Haematological Diseases (HDs), oncological and non-oncological. HDs involve a class of up to 450 disorders in six large groups. The overall number of patients affected with haematological malignancies account about 5% of cancers. Most HDs can cause chronic health problems and many of them are life-threatening conditions requiring numerous resources and multidisciplinary teams, thus representing a public health challenge.

The use cases:

Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS)

Multiple Myeloma (MM)

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)

The Disease

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is a group of hereditary red blood cell disorders. It is a rare, chronic and life-threatening disease. In patients with SCD, red blood cells become C-shaped in resemblance to a sickle, the farming tool the disease is named after. Sickle cells die early and tend to clog the blood flow when going through small blood vessels, so patients usually suffer from low red blood cell counts, infections, acute chest syndrome and strokes.

Clinical Aims

Identify gene mutations associated to high levels of inflammation markers (C-reactive protein - CRP)

SCD patients will be examined for correlations between previously identified genetic inflammatory risk profiles CRP level, aiming to develop high inflammation prediction models.

AI allocation of SCD patients to a sickling risk profile

based on their genomic profile Understand which genetic loci (GWAS) are associated with SCD patient-specific blood rheology and the point of sickling (PoS).

Develop a combined model from inflammation and sickling risks to predict clinical outcome

Using the extent of renal damage (nephropathy) expressed as microalbuminuria as gold standard, together with other known genetic modifiers of SCD severity.

AI-based Radiomics

Build a probability score using AI-based brain MRI image analysis to predict incidents of silent infarction (MRI based outcome) in young SCD patients.

Data

MRI data file (DICOM, CTI, SIGNA etc.), Lorrca Oxygenscan raw data file (RTS, TXT), GWAS data file, laboratory parameters (RTS, XLS etc.), clinical parameters and baseline characteristics (RTS, XLS etc.)

Study design: Multi-centric prospective non-interventional study

Specific objectives

GenoMed4All aims at enabling personalized medicine for SCD patients by the development and validation of AI algorithms combining genomics and other -OMICS data, laboratory data, images, and clinical data.

Study Population

- Number of patients: 1.000 SCD patients
- Regarding gender distribution, SCD affects equally males and females, therefore, we expect our cohort to be gender balanced.

Clinical Partners

1. VHIR (Vall d'Hebron Institut de Recerca)
2. UMCU (Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht)
3. APHP (Assistance Publique – Hôpitaux de Paris)
4. CING (The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics)
5. ESIEE (Chambre de Commerce et d'industrie de Région Paris Ile-De-France)

About the data

This dataset was designed to investigate the genetic and clinical factors influencing Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) severity and outcomes. The experiments focused on key pathological mechanisms such as inflammation, blood rheology, and organ damage to develop predictive models for disease progression.

Genetic analyses identified mutations linked to high levels of inflammation markers, particularly C-reactive protein (CRP), correlating them with known genetic risk profiles

to refine inflammation prediction models. GWAS revealed genetic loci associated with patient-specific blood rheology and the point of sickling (PoS), while AI-based classification stratified patients into sickling risk profiles. A combined model integrating inflammation and sickling risks was developed, using nephropathy severity (microalbuminuria) as a benchmark alongside known genetic modifiers of SCD. Additionally, AI-driven radiomics analysed brain MRI scans to generate probability scores for predicting silent infarctions in young SCD patients. The dataset included multimodal data such as MRI files (DICOM, CTI, SIGNA), Lorrca Oxygenscan raw data, GWAS datasets, and clinical parameters, providing a foundation for AI-driven disease modelling and risk assessment.

Metadata

In the file Genomed4All_SCD_Metadata.xls metadata from SCD use case are reported, as the following excerpt.

→ GROUP: DEMOGRAPHICS

SUB GROUP	ELEMENT NAME	ELEMENT DESCRIPTION / UNITS
2. Patient Status	Date of birth	Patient's date of birth
	Sex	Patient's sex at birth
	Patient status	Patient alive or dead
	Date of death	Patient's date of death
	Main cause of death	What was the main cause of death?
	Visit Date	Date of physical examination
	Length/ Height	Patient's length/ height (cm)
	Weight	Patient weight (kg)
	Diastolic blood pressure	mmHg
	Systolic blood pressure	mmHg
	Heart rate	/min
	Oxygen saturation rate	Measured by pulse oximetry (%)
	Comorbidities	Does the patient have any relevant comorbidity?
	Comorbidities (specify)	Specify which comorbidities does the patient have

Excerpt from SCD Demographics Metadata